

Voting Patterns and Its Determinants in Indian Elections

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Abstract:

People can choose their members for the Lok Sabha, Rajya Sabha, and other legislative bodies, as well as for local governance organisations, through the electoral process. Individuals are members of several social groupings, including classes, tribes, genders, castes, and ethnic or linguistic groups. Their disparities have an impact on how people vote in elections. Voting behaviour describes a person's voting pattern or the things that impact their decision to cast a ballot. Its research elucidates the aspects that impact or affect a voter's choice of ballot. The study of voting behaviour extends beyond the examination of electoral data (shifts), voting records, and statistics. It also discusses psychological issues like voters' perceptions, feelings, and relationships to institutional norms and political behaviour.

Key Words: Election, Voting, Democracy, Behaviour

Introduction

In the modern era of democratic politics, voting is one of the most frequently used expressions. India is home to the largest democracy in the world. Every adult citizen in democratic systems, of which there are many and growing, uses "voting" to express his or her approval or disapproval of policies, programmes, and policies of various political parties, as well as the attributes of the candidates vying to become the representatives of the people.

Methodology

The research paper is based on secondary data. The data is taken from different research reports, journals, websites and research papers, Magazine and daily Newspapers, and other educational text books

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the concept of Election and Voting
2. To understand the Determinants of voting Patterns in India

Concepts of election

In every democracy, elections take place regularly. In the globe, there are more than 100 nations where elections occur to select members of the people. The system by which citizens at regular intervals may select their representatives and switch them when they want is termed as election. Elections are a standardized process by which citizens cast votes and elect members to different government positions. Elections are the foundation of a democracy, wherein the adult population of a nation elects the people's representatives.

Need of elections

- Election is important for the following reason,
- Since elections encourage voters to choose their representatives, who subsequently enact laws on their behalf, they are the most effective instrument of indirect democracy.
- The people in the public will select those who will form the government and take key decisions.

- They will select the political party whose policies will direct the creation of laws and the government.
- We may peacefully switch from one type of government to another thanks to elections. If people are unhappy with the incumbent administration, its policies, or the way it is run, they can always choose a different party to form the government.
- Elections ensure that no government is chosen for an endless duration and turns into a despotic one.
- Elections inspire people to participate in national affairs while continuing to be politically aware and engaged.
- It compels political workers to take action in the interest of the populace.

Concept of Voting

Voting is a process whereby a group, such as an electorate or gathering, gets together to voice their opinions or make a decision as a group, usually after discussions, debates, or election campaigns. Voting is how democracies choose their high office holders. "Constituents" are the people who live in a jurisdiction that an elected official represents; "voters" are the people who choose to cast ballots for the candidates they support. Voter collection methods vary, however while many decision-making methods can also be used as electoral methods, systems that support proportional representation are limited to use in elections. In smaller organisations, voting can take place in a variety of ways: formally, using a ballot to select members of political associations, elect coworkers, or assign responsibilities; informally, using a voice vote or a gesture, such as raising one's hand; or online.

Voting Behaviour in India

The behaviour of voter is influenced by several factors such as religion, caste, community, language, money, policy or ideology, purpose of the polls, extent of franchise, political wave etc. In India following main political and socio-economic factors

which act as determinates of voting behaviours in our Democratic system;

1. Election campaign: In order to sway voters in its favour, every party organises extensive election campaigns. The goal of winning votes, especially floating votes, is achieved through the use of mass rallies, street gatherings, one-on-one meetings, posters, poster wars, movie star speeches, TV and radio broadcasts, newspaper advertisements, pamphlets, processions, and propaganda. Voters' choices are influenced in part by polling campaigns. Through its election campaign, the ruling party always tries to provide the idea that it has a chance to win and can pick up some more votes as some people prefer to align themselves with the side they believe will win.

2. Performance of the Party in Power: Every political party runs for office on the basis of an electoral manifesto, which it is expected to follow through on while in office. People's basic behaviours are greatly influenced by the performance of the ruling party, both good and poor, based only on the electoral promises made and kept. We saw that in 1989 in India, when the Congress (I), which had won a landslide majority in the 1984 elections, was unable to get even a simple majority in the 1989 election due mostly to its inability to function well. The inability of the Congress Party and the Janata Dal to retain their political stability and wield authority contributed to their defeat in 1989 and 1991, respectively. The primary cause of this is a commensurate rise in the number of "floating voters," also known as "switchers," who are primarily young adults from the educated upper middle class who are willing to switch parties based solely on performance.

1. Charm: A crucial component of voting behaviour is People with charisma like Nehru, Indira, Vajpayee, and Modi, as well as a quick shift in voters' opinions in response to their appeals, can be considered as tangible proof of the influence of charisma on our people's voting behaviour. The 1971 election saw the "Garibi Hatao" slogan work wonders; in 1972, the State Assembly elections, the electorate was profoundly influenced by Mrs. Gandhi's character following India's incredible triumph in the Bangladesh War. In the 1977 elections, Jayaprakash Narayan's image had the same impact. The impact of Rajiv Gandhi's and V.P. Singh's respective personas on the 1984 and 1989 elections was similar. Because of Modi's demeanour, the BJP won both the 2014 and 2019 elections as well as numerous state assembly elections across various states.

2. Caste: In India, caste still has an impact on voting habits. It is deeply ingrained in society and serves as a fundamental cornerstone at all societal levels. Caste remains a factor in political activity even though our constitution has numerous sections

that forbid discrimination and action on that basis. One well-known aspect of the Indian political system is the politicisation of caste and casteism in societies. All Indian political parties consider the caste element in the formulation of their policies, plans, and electoral campaigns. When choosing candidates to run for office from a constituency, caste has a role. In the name of caste, votes are required. Election strategy planning frequently makes use of Jat Ki Vot Jat Ko, Brahmin votes vs. Jat votes, Jat votes vs. Ahir votes, etc. Even so The primary language used by voters in rural India is caste. The choice to carry out the Mandal Commission's suggestion to reserve positions for other Backward Classes (castes), as well as the political backlash that followed, bear witness to the persistence of caste as a factor in Indian politics. It is imperative to acknowledge, though, that caste's function as a predictor of voting conduct has been evolving, at least in metropolitan regions.

3. Religion influences: In India, the creation of a secular state that upholds religious freedom, treats all religions equally, and rejects the designation of any one as the official state religion hasn't been able to stop religion from playing a role in influencing political behaviour in general and voting behaviour in particular. One reason why religion continues to influence voting behaviour is the existence of political parties and neo-political organisations associated with specific religions, such as the Muslim League, Akali Dal, Hindu Maha Sabha, Shiv Sena, etc. When vying for votes, the candidates don't think twice about playing the religious card with fellow believers and the secular card with followers of other faith organisations. It's also common practise to use religious locations for political purposes, especially around election time. Voters frequently base their decisions on their religious beliefs.

4. Ideological commitment: The ideological commitment of the voters also effects the voting behaviour most of the voters are crazy about particular ideology and they keep in view the ideology of the candidate and the political party at the time of casting their votes. This fact is applicable to the voters who are the supporter of the leftist parties.

5. Language: India is a multi-lingual state. Linguism also serves as factor in voting behavior. The organization of states on linguistic basis fully reflects the importance of language as a factor of politics in India. There have been problems in states like that of status of one particular language in that state, or relating to the quality of the status of a language of a state. Linguistic interests always influence voting behaviour in national and state level election.

5. Money Factor: India is a poor country with a large number of people living below poverty line.

Money as such plays a vital role in determining voting behaviour of the people in India. A rich candidate or party has always better chances of winning the elections.

6. Sub-Nationalism: Ethnic pluralism, communalism, regionalism and sub-nationalism are the hard realities of Indian society. Of late sub-nationalism has become a crucial factor in influencing the voting behaviour of the people. At times a secessionist group gives a call for the boycott of elections and uses pressure tactics to forces the voters either not to vote in favour of a particular party. Some regional political parties like some fractions of the Alkali Dal, Naga Nationalist Organization, Gorkha League, AASU and AAGSP in Assam.

7. Performance of the Party in Power: Each Political party contests elections on the basis of an election manifesto, and after coming into power, it is expected to fulfil the promises made their in. Good or bad performance of the ruling party, just on the basis of the election promises made and promises actually fulfilled influence the basis behavior of the people in a big way..This has happened mainly because of a corresponding increase in the number of young men and women from educated upper middle class, and are ready to shift their support from one party to another on the basis of their performance.

8. Mass literacy: Mass literacy has been another factor of voting behaviours in India. It is because of this weakness of the people that political parties, communal groups and militant outfits, are in a position to exploit the sentiments of the people in the name of caste, religion, region and other such factor. The votes of the illiterate constitute a big proportion of the votes polled and hence it plays a big role in determining the outcomes of elections.

9. Public Esteem of the Candidate: A candidate report with the people with constituency or his known qualities or contribution in any value spread of activity always acts as a factor of voting behavior. A positive image of a party's candidate is a source of popular support for the party. A voter prefers to vote for a candidate who is approachable and who can help him anyway.

10. Election campaigns: Each party launches a vigorous election campaign for influencing the voters in its favour. Use of such means as mass meetings, street meetings, personal contacts , posters, speeches by film stars, TV and Radio broadcasts, newspaper advertisement, hand bills, processions and propaganda, is made to win votes, particularly the floating votes. Election Campaign in designed to make a voter believe that his interest can be best served by the party, the candidate of the party contesting from his constituency.

Conclusion:

In India, political scientists, sociologists, anthropologists, media houses and political parties have been involved in election studies. During post-Independence India, election studies started in the 1950s since the first general election of 1951-52. But systematic studies of elections began in the 1960s, with the initiative of Rajni Kothari, a scholar in the Centre for the Studies of Developing Societies (CSDS), New Delhi, and Myron Wiener, an American political scientist, who specialised in Indian politics. In the 1980s, Pranoy Roy, Davit Butler and Ashok Lahiri's book *A Compendium of Indian Elections*, gave a new momentum to election studies. But it was since the 1990s that election studies have become a regular feature of studies on electoral politics. The principal reason for this has been the increasing frequency of elections for state assemblies or Lok Sabha. The initiative to start election studies in India in the 1990s was again taken by a team of the scholar led by Yogendra Yadav from the CSDS. The team conduct the election studies under the banner of an organisation known as Lokniti. As members of the CSDS team, scholars from various universities in the country conducted election studies. The methods of doing the election studies mainly include surveys. These surveys are known as National Election Survey (NES). The scholars conduct survey before and after election to ascertain various aspects relating to elections. And the determinants of voting behaviour form an important aspect of NES studies. The findings of these studies have been published in several articles in academic journals, books and print media. Apart from the CSDS, several scholars and media groups, political parties engage in studying determinants of electoral behaviour.

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